

Best Practices in Music Encoding: A Pedagogical Approach to Encoding Works by Carrie Jacobs-Bond

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Abstract: This best practices paper draws on the experience of encoding a small body of musical works by composer Carrie Jacobs-Bond (1862-1946) from archival sources accessed at the Library of Congress. It examines the pedagogical and preservation goals of encoding such a corpus, describes workflow, and discusses the intersection of the project with FAIR and CARE principles.

Keywords: Music Encoding Initiative, FAIR Principles, CARE Principles

1 Introduction

This paper details the best practices and considerations for completing an open-access digital humanities (DH) project using the Music Encoding Initiative (MEI). This project originates from a course at the University of Maryland's Master in Library and Information Science titled "Special Topics in Information Studies; Music Encoding for Preservation and Research." The course examined theoretical concepts on the ethics of archival practices and digital humanities projects and practical applications of skills to encode work from primary sources.

Inspired in large part by Anna Kijas' Rebalancing the Canon project, which encodes musical incipits by "women, people of color, historically marginalized, and underrepresented composers," the class worked together to pick the works of Carrie Jacobs-Bond (CJB) for encoding.⁹ We prioritized open access, grounding our mission in the FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) principles for (meta)data.¹⁰ We will contribute our work

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⁹ "About the project," Rebalancing the Canon, accessed December 6, 2024, <https://rebalancing-music-canon.com/about/>.

¹⁰ "FAIR Principles," GO FAIR, accessed December 6, 2024, <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>.

to Dalia, a resource database that specializes in open access data literacy.¹¹ Although we did not use the work of Indigenous composers, the CARE principles for Indigenous Data Governance (Collective benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) served as guiding principles for conceptualizing the project and understanding broader implications for this type of research.¹²

Throughout the course of this project, students of all skill levels collaboratively learned how to access and handle archival sources, transcribe sheet music using MuseScore, edit both the encoded music and accompanying metadata in the MEI schema, expressed in XML with mei-friendly, and manage projects through Github. We ultimately encoded twenty-two full works from CJB's collection at the Library of Congress (LoC) and published them as open access datasets on Zenodo. This paper will describe the benefits of producing a project like this (pedagogical, preservation, research, and access), the steps taken to accomplish it, and how others could replicate or adapt workflows to other projects. Additionally, after discussing the limitations of our project, we included a section on special considerations for others wanting to do similar work. Our hope is that this paper will serve as a rallying call for expanded use of MEI and open access data, especially to make work from underrepresented groups more accessible, and as a roadmap for how to get started.

2 Project Benefits

2.1 Pedagogical Benefits

Given our group's overall interest in information and data management careers, this project had incredible pedagogical benefits. We applied archival research skills and close reading skills during the material selection and digital transcription processes. We worked collaboratively to troubleshoot challenges we faced while using MuseScore, mei-friendly, and GitHub, and we connected with community stakeholders to ensure we followed best practices throughout our encoding process.

2.1.1 Archival Research Skills

This project gave group members firsthand experience being collaborative archival researchers, which is extremely beneficial for those entering careers in information. For some, the project provided first opportunities to apply archival research skills. Perhaps most practically, we learned how to request a specific collection from the LoC and how to properly handle primary sources. Following the prescribed protocols of the LoC Performing Arts Reading Room, we sat at separate desks and examined our assigned boxes item by

¹¹ Dalia, "Mission and Vision," accessed December 9, 2024, <https://dalia.education/en>.

¹² "CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance," Global Indigenous Data Alliance, accessed December 6, 2024, <https://www.gida-global.org/care>.

item, ensuring continued preservation. As we were working with delicate and rare materials, we had to be thorough but gentle. The condition of the musical manuscripts were quite fragile, with some encased in mylar to prevent further crumbling or tearing. We did not use gloves as decreased tactile faculties could lead to increased damage to materials.¹³ As we worked, group conversation started to reveal which details were most significant to us. We passed along observations regarding dates, titles, margin notes, instrumentation, and lyrics. After scores were selected, scanned, and organized, each group member claimed pieces for transcription and encoding.

2.1.2 Close Reading Skills

Close reading requires mindfulness, discipline, and an intent to view an object's deeper meanings.¹⁴ The nature of this project presented an additional musical layer to these close reading skills. Group members read, as well as played, sang, and listened to CJB's scores in the process of transcribing her works as accurately as possible. Despite individual assignments, group members continued to work collaboratively, especially in instances where handwriting created discrepancies. We had to play the role of "paleographers" at times, as we worked together to decipher CJB's cursive handwriting.¹⁵ A particularly loopy "n" was almost mistaken for a "v," resulting in the word "loveliness" instead of "loneliness." Obviously, this would have completely changed the tone of that particular verse! We also benefited from the variety of our group's musical experiences. For instance, what appeared to one group member to be opposing articulation markings were clarified as bowing specifications by another group member with more string experience.

2.1.3 Transcription

Musical transcription typically describes the act of notating a piece of music that was previously not notated. Our transcription can best be described as the digital transcription of CJB's works. We had the scans of her original, handwritten copies, and it was our task to transcribe her ideas into digital versions. Our group digitally transcribed the scores using MuseScore, an open source musical notation program.

Transcription issues arose when musical ideas that were easily handwritten were not so easily "typed." For instance, when notating a dynamic with paper and pencil, the composer simply writes "f" or "forte" where the forte is meant to begin. Digitally, however, the transcriber has

¹³ Amy Sampson, "Handling historic collections: the gloves are still off," last updated May 31, 2023, <https://blog.nationalarchives.gov.uk/handling-historic-collections-the-gloves-are-still-off/>.

¹⁴ Brummett, Barry. *On Noticing What You See and Hear*. In *Techniques of Close Reading*, Second, 1-24. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781071873083>.

¹⁵ Bullock, Alison. "palaeography." In *The Oxford Companion to Music*. : Oxford University Press, <https://www.oxfordreference.com/view/10.1093/acref/9780199579037.001.0001/acref-9780199579037-e-4947>.

to be very specific and assign the forte to an exact note. Furthermore, changing dynamics, such as crescendos, must have clear starting notes and ending notes. Without assigned beginnings and endings, the MuseScore playback would be inaccurate, as well as the code.

Other struggles occurred with voicing. Again, using paper and pencil, a composer can easily add and remove counter melodies or harmonies with contrasting rhythms. In MuseScore, adding a harmony voice in the middle of a measure adds redundant rests to the measure. Seeing these extra rests in the same staff as the other voice line looks odd though, and it is not how music is typically written. Thus, we had to experiment with adding and removing voice lines, as well as with making certain “extra” symbols invisible in the digital score. Honoring and transcribing CJB’s precise musical ideas and notation was both a musical and technical challenge.

2.1.4 XML and Metadata Generation

For many of us, this was our first time actively working with XML, let alone MEI. As such, this project required us to learn the basics of what XML is used for and what the different components of our MEI output were used for. By the end of it, we were comfortable making changes directly to the code of MEI files with mei-friend and appreciated it as a more efficient alternative to repeatedly updating and exporting with MuseScore. We likewise needed to create a standardized header for our MEI files, requiring a discussion of necessary metadata and how that was expressed in MEI. In addition to our encoded musical scores, a related piece of personal correspondence required learning the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) schema. This posed an additional challenge: deciding whether or not it fell within the scope of this project, and experimenting with TEI to prepare the file for upload.

2.1.5 Software and Technical Troubleshooting

This project required us to develop a workflow that featured three primary digital tools: MuseScore, mei-friend, and GitHub. MuseScore, a notation software, and mei-friend, a popular editor for MEI, are important tools for people working with music and information professionals working on digital humanities projects. We also created and worked with a GitHub repository to store several versions of each piece throughout the encoding project, from our initial XML exported from MuseScore to the final copies after we completed quality assurance. We also gained practical experience committing changes from a code editor and maintaining versions of each piece throughout development, which fostered deeper collaboration and developed skills applicable beyond this specific project.

Most project collaborators had only used one, if any of these tools, requiring us to pose questions to each other and work together to decide the best ways to approach issues. Consulting documentation and online resources for each program was necessary over the

course of the project, as we encountered errors in our XML and in MuseScore. This became an incredibly valuable skill in this project, and it is transferable to learning new software, programming languages, etc. in the future.

2.1.6 Creating Collaborative Workflows and Our Team Charter

In the early stages of the project, the team met to design a project charter inspired by Bethanie Nowviski to define the project components and plan how we would engage with the work.¹⁶ The charter was understood to be a living document that could be adjusted if our needs changed or expanded over the course of the project. It covered topics such as: how and when we would communicate, how we would address issues, and our preferences for working. This was incredibly useful for understanding when people were available and how we could best work together collaboratively.

We also decided that we would need a way to communicate with each other outside of our weekly meeting time and decided to use Discord to leverage our familiarity with the platform. Discord provided flexible customization and the option to use voice channels for discussion or collaboration, if needed. We additionally used our Discord to communicate for purposes beyond the scope of the class project; namely, to share jokes and memes in the grander pursuit of comic relief. We also used Discord to celebrate positive moments and achievements in each other's lives, especially in this season of unprecedented political and economic pessimism. Our group Discord served to strengthen and develop the collaborative spirit as much as possible, which is absolutely essential in any music encoding project. Considering the class' hybrid nature, the channels fostered a positive and inclusive environment, and encouraged stronger collaboration and communication between physically distanced team members.

2.1.7 Engaging with International Community Stakeholders

The Music Encoding Initiative has a large community of users that use and support the MEI guidelines and the tools that interact with it (like mei-friend). Community members are reachable via a Slack channel, and MEI distributes community information and updates using a Listserv. There were several situations throughout the project in which we contacted MEI community members for support when our issues were not resolved by referencing the documentation. This validated the idea that it's often more useful and efficient to reach out to a community of people who have more expertise in a given tool or field, and it gave us valuable networking opportunities.

¹⁶ Bethanie Nowviskie, "Charter-ing A Path," last updated November 21, 2014, <https://nowviskie.org/2014/charter-ing-a-path/>.

While some issues were either solved in a straightforward or eventual manner, such as a simple referral to a missed MEI Guidelines section or getting assistance for a TEI file, others were left inconclusive. One member reached out to the MEI community on Slack regarding an *<arpeg>* issue and did receive an answer, but the proffered solution did not work and the community member did not respond to further questioning. We did not take the radio silence to heart, instead taking into account the time zone differences and possible language barriers.¹⁷

2.2 Preservation Benefits

2.2.1 Preserving Primary Sources

Regarding preservation, the most obvious reason for projects such as ours is less wear on primary documents. Given the age of the materials, CJB's manuscripts are, expectedly, worn. Torn pages, frayed edges, and faded pencil markings were not uncommon. While the Library of Congress has done significant work to preserve CJB's documents, continued physical use and interaction will only exacerbate this concern. Our work to scan and digitally transcribe CJB's music manuscripts for general public access will contribute to preservation efforts.

2.2.2 Open-Source Materials

The shutdown of the notation program, *Finale*, in August 2024 proves the urgent need to move digital music transcriptions out of proprietary software and into open source options. The manuscripts we chose to scan, transcribe, and encode will be available as MEI files, one of the preferred formats by the LoC.¹⁸ Proprietary music notation formats are classified as "acceptable," because the formats are not as accessible to those without subscriptions and continued software updates make older files no longer interoperable. Therefore, using an open source format like MEI was in line with our overall goals of long-term and widespread preservation.

2.3 Research and Access Benefits

Beyond the preservation benefits MEI provides, it also improves the accessibility of data for wider audiences. Digitally available works are generally more accessible to users than those that are only available as physical records in a single location. The pieces are available to a

¹⁷ Most of the professional community on the MEI Slack reside in Germany.

¹⁸ "Recommended Formats Statement," Library of Congress, effective 2024, <https://www.loc.gov/preservation/resources/rfs/musical-scores.html>.

larger geographic range, meaning researchers with diverse skills in various disciplines from all across the globe are able to engage with these materials digitally rather than needing to travel to study them. Encoding using MEI also enables the files to be imported to an engraving tool for playback, allowing audiences and researchers alike to appreciate and use these pieces.

In addition to expanding access to different audiences, using MEI enables these works to be analyzed using computational methods. Since MEI is an XML schema, the components of it are consistently defined and machine-readable. These definitions enable researchers to programmatically iterate over the individual parts and analyze their components.

The structure of an MEI file has several benefits for continued use and reuse. The metadata for each file is listed above its content in a header at the top of the file, which allows researchers to easily reference and access metadata while viewing the piece. This data structure helps researchers access relevant information alongside the piece, such as the MEI version and dates of work—either to account for this information in their research on the contents of the record or to use as separate data for computational analysis. These components being managed as one file also makes it easier to maintain clarity and the organization of digital files when the metadata is affixed to the work, in the same format. Lastly, such a structure is also beneficial for clearly identifying people responsible for working on the piece and what specific tasks they completed in the process, linking the name of contributors, their role, and their ORCID identifier.

3 What We Did

3.1 Getting to the Library of Congress

Ahead of our visit to the LoC, we researched and discussed the biographies of the composers we might want to work on. We had elected to look exclusively at the works of women composers, and selected Carrie Jacobs-Bond and Vivian Fine from a list of eight. Roughly a week ahead of time, we requested the music score boxes from both the Jacobs-Bond and Fine collections through the reference staff. In preparation for our in-person visit, we also pre-registered for readers' cards via the LoC website.

Once we arrived at the LoC, we received our temporary readers' cards. In the Performing Arts Reading Room, the reference staff provided us with the boxes we had requested, and we went through the scores as a group.

3.2 Considerations for Source Material

While working our way through the scores, our group engaged in collaborative discussion about the materials. Everything from interesting titles to intriguing passages came under

discussion, so we created a set of criteria to follow when selecting music from the two collections to scan for potential further use. These criteria included:

- No more than two instruments or four voices;
- No more than 10 pages;
- Representative of the composer's style, voice, etc.; or
- Particular interest to the encoder.

Time was another important consideration that influenced the materials we chose to encode. From the time of material selection to the project due date, we had seven weeks to transcribe all the selected scores into MuseScore, export and edit the files for accuracy in mei-friend, and publish our datasets. This meant that pieces considered too difficult for beginning encoders to transcribe were excluded from our final selections. In fact, the first two selection criteria were devised explicitly for that reason.

The physical state of the manuscript was also taken into consideration. Some manuscripts were encased in mylar to preserve crumbling and damaged paper from further damage. While some of the pre-existing damage did not hinder the legibility of the score, there were cases of pages or entire scores being too damaged to reasonably consider scanning, either having lost whole sections or pages. Additionally, if a piece was not legible when viewing it in person, we reasoned it would be even more difficult to transcribe once in a scanned format. These conditions allowed us to choose the best musical manuscripts for the project without scanning every piece of music we encountered, saving us time in the encoding phase of our work.

Because a primary goal was publishing our datasets open access, we had to consider copyright restrictions. CJB passed away in 1946, meaning all of her work falls within the Public Domain. Vivian Fine, on the other hand, passed away in 2000 and her work is currently under copyright in several places. This meant that publishing the encoded materials would require permission from Fine's estate and any other copyright holder. Given our short timeframe, we chose to encode pieces from the CJB collection, but the group is considering future collaboration using Vivian Fine's work provided permission can be granted.

3.3 Working with Source Material

We scanned any scores we thought would be good candidates for encoding (criteria discussed above) and stored them in a secure institutional Box drive. During our LoC visit, we did not break the scan for each score, instead compiling a few large PDF files that contained multiple scores. As a result, our next task was to break the large PDF files into individual scores.

While doing so, we also created a naming convention that would identify the composer and piece. The naming convention became “INITIALS_TitleOfPiece_YEAR_AdditionalDescriptors.” Some pieces did not have years included on the score, so the year was omitted from those file names. Other descriptors or version numbers were added at the end of the name. Descriptors included “transcribed” and “pencil.” This same naming convention was carried over into both the GitHub repository and the Zenodo deposit.

There were two exceptions to this naming convention. First, we did not realize that there was a file left that contained two scores (Compensation and Democracy) until we had already begun encoding, so we split those scores in the encoding phase. Second, there was a letter written about *An I've Got Home* that, as a letter, did not have a title; that file was titled “CJB_Personal Correspondence,” and the letter was encoded using Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) instead of MEI because it did not have musical notation to encode.¹⁹

4 How It Worked

4.1 Encoding Workflow

Music encoding is a new skill to our class members. Most of the time and work involved in encoding music comes down to transcription; the rest involves editing those transcriptions. So we prepared for our workflow by attempting practice transcriptions and editing sessions of relatively simple scores. After these proved tolerable and engaging, our professor assigned the official workflow. Once we had processed and organized all materials from the LoC, we were ready to encode.

The first step of the encoding workflow was to download chosen pieces from the class repository on GitHub and then use MuseScore to transcribe them as closely as possible. Most (if not all) of the class had prior experience with transcription softwares, MuseScore in particular. This somewhat expedited the process of transcription, though it is an unavoidably and appropriately time-consuming task. Students exported files as uncompressed .xml files after transcribing scores. We did this so that the files would be compatible with mei-friend when it came time to edit them.

Our class then began editing transcriptions in mei-friend, fixing any errors in the code, then saving and downloading the resulting .mei file. We spent one class meeting creating a template header that we would then use to replace the pre-existing header in each transcribed and edited score, inserting specific information wherever possible. We also inserted our individual ORCiDs for each encoded score. The final stage of the encoding workflow was a quality assurance process consisting of a series of peer reviews.

¹⁹ The TEI Infrastructure,” Text Encoding Initiative, accessed December 8, 2024, <https://tei-c.org/release/doc/tei-p5-doc/en/html/ST.html>.

4.2 F.A.I.R./C.A.R.E.

²⁰ Two sets of principles guided our class along the encoding workflow. These principles, better known within the wide world of music librarianship, are memorable because of their convenient acronyms: F.A.I.R. and C.A.R.E. The former set of principles relate more closely to managing and preserving data while the latter deals more with humans relating to said data.

F.A.I.R. spells out the tenets of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability. Findable data must be unique, persistent, and repeatedly findable. Accessible data must be readable to both computers and the humans that use them. Interoperable data must use a shared vocabulary across different forms of technology. Reusable data refers to the ease of preservability of such data. We met these standards by contributing new research with our project, by editing the code and headers of scores, by utilizing multiple kinds of software as described earlier, and by simply publishing our project, respectively.

C.A.R.E. encompasses the concepts of Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics. Collective benefit refers to the ultimate goal of equitable outcomes for all who contribute or relate to the project. Authority to Control simply means that researchers have the authority to control and access their data. Responsibility refers both to the sharing of critical information from new research and to the importance of responsible behavior of researchers between each other and collaborators to ensure a quality result. Ethics refers to the implementation of social justice in conducting and publishing research. Luckily, our project did not have complex problems that could result in unjust outcomes. We met the remaining standards by controlling and accessing our data after publishing, by creating and abiding by a charter, collaborating through Discord, and by choosing to encode music only by women composers, respectively.

4.3 ORCID

²¹ ORCIDs, or Open Researcher and Contributor IDs, are numerical signatures that identify creators of scholarly research. They typically consist of a string of 16 digits punctuated with hyphens (i.e. 5555-5555-5555-5555). They are free for the general public to obtain and use. Each student in our class obtained an ORCID in the beginning of the semester and added it to the headers we inserted into our newly encoded scores. This connects us with the research we produce beyond merely using name, title, or institution, meaning we will remain distinctly identified from people who share our names. ORCIDs also circumvent the inconsistencies of naming conventions and transferring between writing systems.

²⁰ Joshua Neumann, Kristina Richts-Matthaei, and Nikolaos Beer, "Toward a community model of scholarly editing: FAIR/CARE, research ethics, & labour visibility," *Journal of New Music Research* (2024): 1–19, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298215.2024.2373049>.

²¹ ORCID, accessed December 9, 2024, <https://orcid.org/>.

4.4 Publication and Access

Our dataset of MEI-encoded works and this co-authored paper are available as Open Educational Resources (OER) on Zenodo. This practice is central to our goals of digitally preserving music and supporting accessible avenues for research and collaboration. By leveraging Zenodo’s open access framework, we aim to make these works widely accessible to interested researchers and scholars, as well as bring attention to the musical legacy of Carrie Jacobs-Bond. The publication process begins with a final quality assurance checkpoint, including both an evaluation of the encoding and the associated metadata. The metadata, created according to FAIR principles, ensures discoverability and provides context to scholars.

One of the fundamental principles of this project is commitment to open access. By publishing our work under a Creative Commons License, we ensure that the MEI-encoded works and Open Educational Resource can be freely viewed, shared, and used for further research. Zenodo’s platform enables us to cite materials properly and integrate them into other scholarly work, maximizing their visibility and potential research impact. To prepare for publication, we ensured that all materials were properly organized and accessible in user-friendly formats, facilitating seamless viewing, sharing, and use for future research. Furthermore, by contributing to the DALIA project, we aim to uphold these principles by contributing to the democratization of cultural and scholarly data and encouraging greater collaboration within academic communities.²²

5 Special Considerations

Our team recognized the complexity of the art of music combined with technology and was careful to consider the numerous factors surrounding musical DH projects throughout our own project. We paid special attention to the different “-scriptions”—particularly: prescription, description, transcription, and inscription—and how they would impact the way we worked. Indeed, keeping these cognates in mind helped us comprehend the significance of various stages of our workflow. The pieces we transcribed digitally were originally handwritten manuscripts. These manuscripts were our prescription, as our transcription had to be exactly the same as, or as close as possible to, the original work. The header that we created for every single piece describes all the contributions made towards this project, including the original work of the composer, Carrie Jacobs-Bond, by our class in the Fall semester of 2024. Our end goal was to publish (or rather, to “inscribe”) our work on Zenodo under a Creative Commons license.

²² “Mission & Vision | DALIA,” accessed December 8, 2024, <https://dalia.education/en>.

5.1 Collaborators

The team had to consider the ethics of crediting all contributors, learned through our discussions on the FAIR and CARE principles. There is at least one contributor per music composition—the composer. Often, numerous collaborators contribute to the creation of a work. Some roles include, but are not limited to: a lyricist/librettist, dedicatee, commissioner, transcriber, engraver, performers, arranger, sound engineer, recording engineer, and publisher. Sometimes some of these collaborators are anonymous; often, even the composer of the piece is anonymous themselves. How, then, can we give credit where it is due in the metadata?

Several members encountered issues when crediting the collaborators to their respective manuscripts. While certain people were explicitly credited as lyricists or arrangers on Carrie Jacobs-Bond's original manuscripts (e.g., Mrs. E.C. Pierce from *O Haunting Memory* and William Mell Butler from *Democracy*, etc.), they did not have their own name authority files in the LoC and thus were unable to be properly cited in the metadata. This created a dilemma for us after we learned the foundational significance of the CARE principles, which emphasize justice specifically in the E, for ethics. Unfortunately, there was no true solution for this dilemma, though we hope that future projects and increased awareness of the issue will contribute to growing consideration of the people involved in the creation of musical works.

5.2 Interpretations

Our project team made use of the written manuscripts of Carrie Jacobs-Bond, but not every project enjoys such a convenient privilege. Some works are captured and shared via recordings. Transcribing recordings or by ear would require advanced training and music theory experience, something not many of our team possessed.

Orally transmitted works present another challenge. In this model, musical material is passed through generations of a social group; over time, they may gain cultural and historical significance but melodic or harmonic details and lyrics may fluctuate over time. Consider the impact of colonization on the Indigenous groups of North America. Contemporary Indigenous communities are endeavoring to rectify the centuries of oppression and cultural erasure inflicted upon them. Transcribing folk songs and hymns passed down through families or communities presents an especially interesting potential to document possible regional differences, vocal techniques, or dialects. In each of these scenarios, continual reference to the CARE principles would benefit researchers and digital humanities practitioners in their efforts to amplify the voices of the people whose work they study.

Another challenge would be tackling genres of music where ad-libs or improvisation are prevalent, such as jazz, Hindustani music, self-written cadenzas in classical solo repertoire, and so many more. The nature of improvisation poses quite a challenge for potential

transcribers and would require a well-trained ear to effectively encode. Thankfully, we did not encounter such advanced issues, but keeping the possibilities in mind made us all the more grateful for the comparatively minor problems we encountered in our own project.

5.3 Audience

The first, most obvious audience that we considered was musicians of the general public. Carrie Jacobs-Bond was a prolific and very popular composer of her time, but not many recordings of her music currently circulate on the internet. Once published on Zenodo, our digitally transcribed collection of her works would be easily accessible by any musician wishing to revive her sound. The music would be readable with no cause for confusion, unlike our previous struggles with deciphering her handwriting.

The purpose of encoding and publishing the transcribed music in this format is meant to create preserved versions that are also machine readable. Merely creating printed versions would be easily completed in MuseScore, Sibelius, Dorico, or other notation formats. Through encoding, skills in archival study, close reading, and transcription were gained, and through publication, new computational research becomes possible.

The final collection is published on Zenodo, which, as stated before, is free for public use. Despite our original intent for our work to be used in performances and research, how our project's data is used ultimately depends on the general public that it is now available to. We can only be satisfied with the conviction that we brought some of Carrie Jacobs-Bond's work to light, no matter what it might be used for in the future. We hope that this paper inspires others to interact with CJB work and with our datasets, and to expand on this work with additional projects.

6 Conclusion

Encoding this sample of Carrie Jacobs-Bond's works presented many challenges, but the successes and new opportunities for information and data access far outweigh the challenges and difficulties. It is our hope that our experiences with this project will encourage others to embark upon similar projects. Expanding the use of MEI in information communities, especially archival ones, will enable increased preservation of and access to the musical works of all composers—especially those who were or are part of marginalized groups.